

Polarographic study of [Cd–L-amino acidate–vitamin B₁] system

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Polarographic technique has been used to determine the stability constants ($\log \beta$) of Cd^{II} complex with glycine, α -alanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-asparagine and L-glutamine as primary ligands and vitamin B₁ (thiamine) as secondary ligand at pH 8.50 \pm 0.01 and the ionic strength $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO₃). Cd^{II} forms 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes at 25°.

L-Amino acids are biologically active having considerable interest in their metal complexes¹. They have good chelating ability with metal ions and play an important role in biology, pharmacy and as laboratory reagents². Ternary complexes of Cd^{II} have been studied with glycine, α -alanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-asparagine and L-glutamine as primary ligands and vitamin B₁ (thiamine) as secondary ligand. In continuation of our earlier work³ on Mn^{II}, the values of stability constant of ternary complexes and the effects of size and basicity of primary ligands on their solution stability of complexes are determined.

Results and Discussion

A well defined two-electron reversible reduction wave of Cd^{II} was observed in KNO₃⁴ for all the complexes. The plots of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs E_{de} gave straight-lines with slopes

30 \pm 2 mV.

Ternary complexes were investigated at two definite concentrations of vitamin B₁ (viz. 0.025 and 0.050 mol dm⁻³) and varying the concentration of L-amino acids (viz. from 0.5 to 30 mmol dm⁻³). The amino acids chosen were glycine, α -alanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-asparagine and L-glutamine. In each of the mixed system, a shift in the half wave potential to more negative side was observed on increasing the concentration of L-amino acids while keeping the concentration of vitamin B₁ constant.

The overall stability constants of ternary complexes determined by the graphical extrapolation method of Schaap and McMaster technique⁵, confirmed the formation of 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes. The polarographic characteristics and $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ of [Cd-glycinate-vita-

Table 1 Polarographic characteristics and $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ values for the Cd^{II}–glycinate–vitamin B₁ system
[Cd^{II}] = 0.5 mmol dm⁻³, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$ (KNO₃), pH = 8.50 \pm 0.01, $-E_{1/2}$ Cd^{II} = 0.586 V vs SCE, Temp = 25°

[Gly] $\times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$	Vitamin B ₁ = 0.025 mol dm ⁻³ (fixed)						Vitamin B ₁ = 0.050 mol dm ⁻³ (fixed)					
	$\Delta E_{1/2}$	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_{00}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-1}$	$F_{10}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$F_{20}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-7}$	$F_{30}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-8}$	$\Delta E_{1/2}$	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_{00}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-1}$	$F_{10}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-5}$	$F_{20}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-8}$	$F_{30}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-8}$
0.00												
0.50	0.050	0.007	4.99	8.74	7.09	43.70	0.080	0.014	53.87	10.49	13.37	43.65
1.00	0.062	0.014	13.13	12.51	7.31	43.73	0.095	0.014	173.42	17.20	13.39	43.61
2.00	0.077	0.014	41.99	20.68	7.74	43.62	0.111	0.022	615.08	30.68	13.44	43.59
3.00	0.086	0.021	89.84	29.74	8.18	43.68	0.121	0.022	1328.89	44.25	13.48	43.67
4.00	0.093	0.029	159.22	39.65	8.61	43.56	0.127	0.038	2317.76	57.91	13.52	43.71
5.00	0.099	0.037	252.76	50.43	9.05	43.51	0.133	0.038	3583.77	71.62	13.57	43.51
6.00	0.104	0.044	373.01	62.06	9.48	43.46	0.137	0.045	5129.80	85.47	13.61	43.77
8.00	0.112	0.044	704.11	87.93	10.34	43.40	0.144	0.053	9073.01	113.39	13.70	43.52
10.00	0.118	0.044	1172.82	117.22	11.20	43.32	0.150	0.053	14166.39	141.65	13.78	43.40
20.00	0.140	0.052	6331.82	316.56	15.57	43.49	0.168	0.061	57653.79	288.26	14.22	43.63
30.00	0.153	0.061	18052.22	601.72	19.88	43.38	0.178	0.069	133090.69	443.63	14.66	43.69
		$\log A = 0.793$		$\log C = 7.84$				$\log A = 1.143$		$\log C = 8.130$		
		$\log B = 4.716$		$\log D = 9.64$				$\log B = 5.581$		$\log D = 9.630$		

Note

min B₁] are presented in Table 1. The values of stability constants of [Cd-L-amino acidate-vitamin B₁] system are presented in Table 2.

(calculated) effective mercury height. pH was measured with an Elico-LI 120 pH meter fitted with glass and saturated calomal electrodes. All the measurements were made at 25°.

Table 2. pK values and stability constants of [Cd-L-Amino acidate-vitamin B₁] system

[Cd^{II}] = 0.5 mmol dm⁻³, μ = 1.0 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃), pH = 8.50 ± 0.01, Temp. = 25°

Ligands	pK ₂ ^H	log β ₀₁ ^a	log β ₀₂ ^a	log β ₁₀ ^b	log β ₂₀ ^b	log β ₃₀ ^b	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁	log K _m
Glycine	9.80	–	–	4.30	7.60	9.64	5.41	8.61	10.41	–0.03
α-Alanine	9.40	–	–	4.23	7.46	9.43	5.24	–	10.17	–0.13
L-Leucine	9.74	–	–	4.17	7.35	9.34	4.77	7.81	9.80	–0.64
L-Valine	9.71	–	–	4.11	7.21	9.16	4.61	–	–	–0.54
L-Asparagine	8.80	–	–	4.07	7.18	9.10	4.56	7.46	9.51	–0.77
L-Glutamine	9.13	–	–	4.00	7.04	8.91	4.40	7.21	–	–0.67
Vitamin B ₁	–	2.20	3.30	–	–	–	–	–	–	–

^aRef. 9. ^b Ref. 10.

The stability of the ternary complexes were compared with that of the binary complexes and the values of mixing constant (log K_m)⁶ are shown in Table 2. The enhanced stability of ternary complexes relative to the binary complexes might be due to the entropy effect arising from lower charge on the mixed complexes⁷. The trend of the stability constants of complexes was found to be L-glutamine < L-asparagine < L-valine < L-leucine < α-alanine < glycine, which is in accordance with the nature of bonding and basicities of these ligands. Similar trends were observed in case of Mn^{II}³ and some other transition metal complexes^{8,9}.

Experimental

L-Amino acids (Loba Chem) and vitamin B₁ (Fluka) were used. All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The concentrations of metal ions, KNO₃ and gelatin in the test solution were 0.5 mmol dm⁻³, 1.0 mol dm⁻³, and 0.001%, respectively. The test solutions were deaerated by passing pure H₂ before recording the polarograms. pH of the test solutions were adjusted to 8.50 ± 0.01 by adding requisite amount of NaOH or HCl solutions.

The current-voltage curves were obtained on a manual polarograph using a Toshniwal (PL-60) polyflex galvanometer (PL-50). The dropping mercury electrode had capillary characteristics of $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 60.02 cm

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